

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF THE STATUS OF ATTRACTING CAPITAL INVESTMENTS IN MODERNIZATION OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

Under the former administrative-command system, when enterprises operating in industrial sectors were state-owned, the main source of investment was state (budget) funds. Although even in those conditions, savings funds - the main investment sources - were made at the expense of the profits (income) of enterprises, enterprises did not have a "headache" about where to get funds and where to invest them. An additional source was the depreciation fund of enterprises.

Introduction. Today, the development of industry and its branches is becoming an urgent problem. In the planning and management system, both internal and external types of determining investment sources are also used. As we know, internal sources of investment include:

- the enterprise's own financial resources, formed as a result of depreciation deductions for working capital;
- part of the profit allocated for investment needs;
- funds paid by insurance companies and institutions in case of natural disasters and other events;
- funds received as a result of the issue and sale of shares by the enterprise;
- funds allocated on a non-repayable basis by higher and other bodies;
- donations and other similar funds.

External sources of investment include:

- non-repayable funds allocated from the central and local budgets, various funds supporting entrepreneurship;
- foreign investments made in the form of financial or other material and immaterial participation in the capital of enterprises, as well as direct investments of international financial institutions and individuals;
- loans provided by the state and various funds with the condition of repayment, including preferential loans.

In the conditions of independent economic activity of enterprises, depreciation allowances occupy a key place in the structure of internal funds. Its share in the investment

resources of the enterprise is 50% or more. In conditions of a shortage of funds for investment purposes, leasing serves as an important tool for activating investment activity. The main areas of use of investments (capital investments) are:

- new construction;
- expansion and reconstruction of the enterprise;
- modernization and technical re-equipment of production;
- improvement of operational capacities.

We should pay attention to the following in the process of conducting the analysis. New construction includes enterprises, buildings, structures and devices built on specially developed projects in new areas.

Expansion of an operating enterprise means the construction of additional parts of additional production complexes on a new project or the expansion or construction of existing workshops of the main, additional, auxiliary and service production. It is carried out mainly on the territory of the operating enterprise or in adjacent areas.

Restoration means the complete or partial transformation of an operating enterprise by replacing morally and physically obsolete devices and equipment with mechanization and automation of production, elimination of imbalances in technological units and auxiliary services. During reconstruction, it is allowed to build new workshops instead of old ones.

Technical re-equipment is a set of measures to increase the technical level of the enterprise by introducing new equipment and technologies into individual types of production based on modern requirements, mechanization and automation of production processes, updating and replacing obsolete equipment and devices, improving the structure and organization of production. It is aimed at increasing production intensity, increasing production capacity and improving the quality of manufactured products.

The issues of analyzing indicators representing financial results in economic entities occupy a special place in the scientific works of foreign and CIS economists I. Belolipetsky, I. Bocharov, N. L. Brook, A. Bernstein, M. I. Bakanov, L. I. Kravchenko, V. V. Kovalev, A. I. Merkushev, V. Paliy, S. K. Tatur, V. V. Kovalev, M. Meskon, B. Needles, A. D. Sheremets. Among the economists of our republic E. A. Akramov, B. A. Khasanov, A. V. Vahabov, R. A. Dosmuratov, YE. YE. Yergeshev, A. T. Ibrohimov, B. I. Isroilov, M. Q. Pardayev, M. M. Tolakhodzhayeva, A. Kh. Shoalimov, V. V. Ergashboyev and others.

In the scientific works of these economists, some problems and organizational aspects of the analysis of financial results at enterprises in the conditions of transition to a market economy were studied. Improving the methods of analyzing financial results at enterprises is a topic of urgent scientific and practical importance. Taking this into account, in this work, indicators representing profit and profitability were studied in a comprehensive and systematic manner.

Research methodology. The research work used observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, induction, deduction, chain substitution, absolute differentiation and other economic and statistical methods.

Profit from the main production activity includes the profit received from the main production activity of the enterprise, other than the production and sale of products. They are included in the statement of financial results in a total amount, separately, along with

the expenses and income. It is determined that operating income and expenses are also included in the statement of financial results at their net value. In this case, income from operating processes is included in the statement of profit or loss, differentiated from the cost of expenses on them.

To determine the profit from the main activity, it is recommended to deduct period expenses and other expenses from the main activity from the gross profit from the sale of products, and add income from other activities.

When assessing the profit (loss) received from the main activity of the enterprise and the factors affecting its change, it is necessary to analyze period expenses, other income from the main activity and expenses.

Under the term period costs, we mean costs and expenses that are not directly related to the production process. Period costs include business expenses that are not included in the cost of production of products. Depending on the form and place of their occurrence, they can be divided into the following:

Selling expenses - expenses included in the cost of products (works, services), are classified in a unified manner in accordance with the Regulation on the composition of costs for the production and sale of products and the procedure for the formation of financial results and are directly related to the effectiveness of the enterprise's activities.

Selling expenses include expenses associated with the delivery and sale of products to buyers and customers. Selling expenses can be divided and analyzed into wage costs, deductions from wages, material costs, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets, advertising costs, work and services, and other cost items.

Administrative expenses include expenses related to the management of the enterprise, and their share in the structure of enterprise expenses is significant. These are the costs of direct services of managers and management staff.

Income and expenses from other processes of the main activity are often also called operating income and expenses. Operating expenses and income include income from other sales or losses on them.

The following are expenses of the enterprise other than the main activity:

expenses for training and retraining of personnel;

expenses for eliminating defects in design and construction and installation works;

fees for consulting and information systems;

fees for auditing services;

expenses for health protection and organization of recreation activities not related to the direct participation of employees in the production process;

compensation and incentive payments;

expenses not taken into account when calculating wages, i.e. material assistance;

expenses for maintaining temporarily suspended production capacities and facilities;

contributions to health, public education, social security and similar organizations;

mandatory payments to the budget, taxes and fees and allocations to extra-budgetary funds;

damages, fines, penalties and other expenses.

Other income from the main production activity includes:

finances and penalties collected or recognized by the debtor;
profits of the previous year determined in the reporting year;
income from auxiliary service industries;
income from the sale of fixed assets, intangible assets and other property;
income from the write-off of overdue accounts payable and depositor debts;
results of the revaluation of tangible assets;
income from state subsidies;
objective financial assistance;
other operating income.

As a result of research conducted on factor analysis of indicators representing financial results, scientific conclusions and practical proposals were developed on the use of analytical methods in determining the internal opportunities for stabilizing the financial activities of the enterprise and increasing its economic efficiency:

The socio-economic essence, tasks of profit in the conditions of economic liberalization were indicated and scientific definitions were given. In particular, it was theoretically proven that the interest of society, the team and each individual in receiving profit is an objective necessity.

Methods for calculating factors affecting the change in gross profit from the sale of products were recommended. At the end of 2024, gross profit in business entities decreased by 13,466 thousand soums compared to the beginning of the year, or its growth rate was 96.68%. The decrease in gross profit was due to an increase in the cost of goods sold.

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